

SUBSTITUTION REACTIONS OF 2-ACETAMIDO-THIAZOLES. PART I

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Substitution reactions of 2-acetamido-thiazoles with mercuric chloride have been studied with the introduction of chloromercuri group into the thiazole nucleus, and evidence furnished as to its position. By cleavage of chloromercuri group, the chloromercuri compounds have been converted into the corresponding 5-bromo-, 5-iodo-, 5-thiocyanato-thiazoles.

In course of our studies on mercuration of *sec.*- and *tert.*-thiazolylamines, it was observed that the acetoxymercuri group entered the aryl nucleus without affecting the thiazole nucleus. This, however, encouraged us to study the effect of other mercuring agents like $HgCl_2$ on the thiazole nucleus. Since the amino group had to be protected by acetylation during mercuration, the investigation provided scope to determine if amido group (like the amino group which is known to activate an aromatic molecule sufficiently for condensation reaction) might also be capable enough to bring about activation of the thiazole molecule.

Mercuration actually occurred with $HgCl_2$, resulting in introduction of a chloromercuri group. The chloromercuri group is assumed to substitute H of C_5 , on the basis of the following considerations. Evidence for the amino group in 2-position in 2-aminothiazoles, activating the carbon atom in position-5, is provided by several experimental facts (Bogert and Chertcoff, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 2864; Ganapati and Venkataraman, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, **22A**, 348; Beyer and Wolter, *Ber.*, 1952, **85**, 1077). Condensation with chlorosulphonic acid also occurs in the same position (Faith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2063). This is according to expectations, since it has been observed frequently that sulphur in cyclic union is the equivalent of $CH=CH$ group, as is well illustrated in close parallelism in physical and chemical properties between the benzene and the thiophene series or between the thiazoles themselves and the corresponding pyridines. So the carbon atom at position-5 may be regarded to be in *para* position to the amino group in 2-aminothiazoles, and is therefore expected to take part in all condensation reactions. These considerations may be safely extended to acetamido group placed in position-2.

The chloromercuri group is, however, very labile and can be easily split off. Cleavage of chloromercuri group with Br_2 , I_2 , thiocyanogen (Na-thiocyanate and Br_2) furnished the corresponding 5-bromo, 5-iodo and 5-thiocyanato compounds. The 5-thiocyanato compound was subsequently converted into 5-mercapto compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Amino-4-(β-naphthyl)-thiazole.—A mixture of 2-acetonaphthone (10 g.), iodine (14 g.) and thiourea (10 g.) was intimately mixed with 20-25 c.c. of benzene and heated

with and for some time without the condenser on the water-bath for about 16 hours. In order to remove iodine and excess of the ketone, ether was added, left overnight and ether decanted off. The residue was then extracted with boiling water two or three times and filtered hot each time. To the hot filtrate excess of ammonia was added, when a gummy mass was obtained which solidified on keeping overnight. A yellowish hard solid mass was obtained which was filtered. The solid was recrystallised from alcohol and dried, m.p. 135°, yield 82.7%. (Found: N, 12.48; S, 14.12. $C_{11}H_{10}N_2S$ requires N, 12.38; S, 14.16 per cent).

2-Acetamido-4-(β-naphthyl)-thiazole.—2-Amino-4-(β-naphthyl)-thiazole (5 g.) was taken in a dry flask and sufficient acetic anhydride was added to dissolve it. The mixture was heated gently under reflux. After an hour's heating, the mixture was poured into cold water when a gummy mass was obtained. The supernatant liquid was decanted off and ammonia was added to the gummy mass and left overnight. It was filtered and dried, m.p. 284°, yield 87.7%. (Found: S, 12.08. $C_{15}H_{12}ON_2S$ requires S, 11.94 per cent).

5-Chloromercuri-2-acetamido-4-(β-naphthyl)-thiazole.—To the acetylated compound (1.5 g.), dissolved in alcohol (20 c.c.), mercuric chloride (3 g.) in 25 c.c. of water was added along with sodium acetate (3 g.). The mixture was refluxed for ½ hour over a small flame, cooled and filtered. The solid was transferred to a beaker and was heated with alcohol and dried; yield 65%, m.p. 160°. (Found: Hg, 39.36. $C_{15}H_{11}O_2NS.HgCl$ requires Hg, 39.88 per cent).

5-Bromo-2-acetamido-4-(β-naphthyl)-thiazole.—A mixture of the mercurated compound (1 g.) and methanol (14.5 c.c.), saturated with sodium bromide, was treated with bromine (0.7 g.). After 15 minutes, some sodium sulphite was added, the mixture heated to boiling and filtered. The filtrate was diluted with an equal volume of water and concentrated to about 5 c.c. Water was added to the solution and the solid separating was crystallised from acetic acid; yield 65%, m.p. 135°. The product showed positive test for bromine and negative for mercury. (Found: Br, 23.45; S, 9.12. $C_{15}H_{11}ON_2BrS$ requires Br, 23.05; S, 9.22 per cent).

5-Iodo-2-acetamido-4-(β-naphthyl)-thiazole.—A mixture of the mercurated compound (1 g.), KI (1.1 g.), water (about 8 c.c.) and iodine (0.36 g.) was triturated and filtered. The residue was transferred to a beaker, treated with alcohol (30 c.c.) and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to 15 c.c. On cooling, crystals of 5-iodo compound separated out, m.p. 132°, yield 55%. (Found: I, 32.81. $C_{15}H_{11}ON_2IS$ requires I, 32.23 per cent).

5-Thiocyanato-2-acetamido-4-(β-naphthyl) thiazole.—To a mixture of the mercurated compound (1.2 g.) and sodium thiocyanate (0.65 g.) in 20 c.c. of acetic acid, a solution of bromine (0.58 g.) in acetic acid (10 c.c.) was added. The mixture was allowed to stand for about 15 minutes and then filtered. Approximately 35 c.c. of water was added to the filtrate and the mixture was evaporated to dryness. The residue was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 300°, yield 60%. (Found: N, 12.75; S, 20.08. $C_{15}H_{11}ON_2S_2$ requires N, 12.92; S, 19.69 per cent).

TABLE I

Nature of the substituent.	2-Acetamido-4-aryl-5-thiazole mercuric chloride.			2-Acetamido-4-aryl-5-bromo-thiazole.		
	M.P.	% Mercury.		M.P.	% Halogen.	
		Found.	Calc.		Found.	Calc.
Phenyl	294-96°	44.52	44.28	185°	27.42	26.93
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	290°	41.28	41.53	130°	24.02	24.46
2-Thienyl	245°	43.25	43.57	230°	26.92	27.30

TABLE II

Nature of the substituent.	2-Acetamido-4-aryl-5-iodo-thiazole.			2-Acetamido-4-aryl-5-thiocyanato thiazole.		
	M.P.	% Halogen.		M.P.	% Sulphur.	
		Found.	Calc.		Found.	Calc.
Phenyl	220-22°	36.58	36.91	177°	22.80	23.27
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	212°	33.38	33.95	160°	20.60	20.98
2-Thienyl	116°	36.10	36.30	300°	33.95	34.20

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